

BEYOND AUTOMATION: THE IMPACT OF ANTHROPOMORPHIC GENERATIVE AI ON CONVERSATIONAL MARKETING

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ABSTRACT

The evolution of conversational marketing has been significantly impacted by Generative AI and anthropomorphic design. This study provides an inclusive review of the literature on the integration of Generative AI and anthropomorphic design in conversational marketing. Initially, the paper explores the concept of anthropomorphism and its psychological drivers, highlighting its role in enhancing the user experience by fostering a sense of familiarity. The incorporation of Generative AI in this paradigm has led to the creation of conversational agents capable of generating human-like, contextually accurate responses, thus transforming the marketing automation landscape. The research investigates the implications of anthropomorphic Generative AI on customer engagement and marketing efficacy. It emphasises the potential benefits, mainly improved user interaction and satisfaction, along with the potential challenges. At the end of this review, it highlights the need for a balanced approach to anthropomorphism in conversational marketing. The paper proposes that conversational agents' design and capabilities must align harmoniously with user expectations to mitigate user dissonance or perceived deception. Given the critical insights drawn from the literature, the paper ends with a research proposal focusing on exploring effective strategies to harmonise user expectations and the capabilities of anthropomorphic conversational agents. This proposed research will provide practical insights for marketers, developers, and researchers looking to navigate the challenges at the intersection of anthropomorphism, Generative AI, and conversational marketing.

Keywords: Generative AI, Anthropomorphism, Conversational Marketing, Customer Engagement, User Experience, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

The advent of Anthropomorphic Generative AI has initiated a paradigm shift in conversational marketing, marking a milestone in the evolution of customer-business interaction. The transformation arises from AI's ability to simulate human-like dialogues, offering a more personalized and engaging conversational experience. However, this integration of human-like characteristics in AI systems has given rise to unique challenges and ethical considerations.

In this context, the primary focus of this exploration is to understand the implications of Anthropomorphic Generative AI in conversational marketing, while navigating the challenges it presents. Key considerations include managing the delicate balance between anthropomorphization and user expectations, addressing the "uncanny valley" phenomenon, and considering the ethical ramifications of AI-human interaction.

Furthermore, an array of potential future research directions is proposed. These proposals aim to provide a comprehensive roadmap for advancing the understanding of anthropomorphic AI's role in conversational marketing. It covers areas like user preferences, ethical implications, cultural factors, and more.

As the world ventures into the era of sophisticated AI, this paper aims to shed light on the transformative potential and challenges of integrating Anthropomorphic Generative AI into the conversational marketing landscape.

The Evolution and Impact of Conversational Marketing

Historically, the traditional marketing landscape predominantly functioned in a broadcast manner, wherein businesses disseminated promotional information, and consumers were primarily passive recipients of these messages. This one-way marketing communication was prevalent across various mediums – print, television, radio, and even early digital platforms. While this approach allowed businesses to reach a large audience, it lacked personalization and direct engagement with customers.

However, the advent of the digital era and the proliferation of social media platforms have transformed the marketing landscape, which is later called *Digital Marketing* (Puri, 2020). Customers today are more empowered and expect personalized, engaging experiences. They desire two-way interactions where their voices are heard, their queries are answered promptly, and their feedback is valued. This paradigm shift led to the emergence of conversational marketing - an approach that emphasizes direct and meaningful dialogues between businesses and customers (Cancel & Gerhardt, 2019).

Conversational marketing is a customer-centric, dialogue-driven approach that seeks to engage customers through meaningful, interactive conversations in real time (Cancel & Gerhardt, 2019; Israfilzade, 2021). Breaking away from conventional, one-sided marketing communications, it seeks to engage customers by using the power of conversations to convey information, address queries, and gather feedback, thereby fostering deeper, more personal connections with customers.

Therefore, the following is a definition of conversational marketing that can be identified in the current paper:

"Conversational marketing is a contemporary marketing approach predicated on real-time, personalized one-to-one interactions across diverse channels, facilitating collaborative brand experiences and

thereby strengthening customer relationships and enhancing overall customer experience."

This slightly revised definition was first presented in the paper "*Conversational marketing as a framework for interaction with the customer*" by author Israfilzade (2021).

Conversational marketing harnesses the power of *dialogue* to not just convey information but to engage customers on a deeper level. It's a dynamic process wherein customers become active participants rather than passive receivers. The conversations are tailored to each customer's context, thereby making the interaction more relevant, personal, and engaging (Zhang et al., 2018; Shumanov & Johnson, 2021).

Through these interactive dialogues, businesses can gain valuable insights into customers' needs, preferences, and pain points. These insights, in turn, can be used to improve product offerings, develop personalized marketing strategies, and deliver better customer service. Therefore, conversational marketing isn't just about promoting products or services, but it's about understanding and engaging with customers, solving their problems, and building lasting relationships (Van Doorn et al., 2017).

The Advent of Generative AI in Conversational Marketing

Artificial intelligence (AI) has dramatically reshaped various domains, with marketing being no exception. Over the last decade, AI technologies have seeped into every facet of marketing, from data analysis and customer segmentation to content creation and personalized advertising. Amid these advancements, the emergence of Generative AI has significantly transformed the realm of conversational marketing (Kulkarni et al., 2019; Mayahi & Vidrih, 2022).

Unpacking Generative AI. Generative AI is a branch of artificial intelligence that uses machine learning algorithms to generate new data from an initial set of input data. In essence, it allows machines to create content that is not only similar to the training data but also novel and unique. This is achieved by training the AI models on vast datasets, enabling them to learn and mimic the patterns, nuances, and complexities of the data (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Houde et al., 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Generative AI creates new content, chat responses, designs, synthetic data, or deepfakes, while traditional AI focuses on patterns, decision-making, analytics, and fraud detection. Generative AI starts with user input and explores content variations, while traditional AI processes new data to produce simple results (Israfilzade, 2020)

There are various models of Generative AI, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Transformer-based models like GPT (Generative Pretrained Transformer) by OpenAI. Each of these models has its strengths and applications. For instance, GANs are often used for generating realistic images, while Transformer-based models like GPT excel in generating human-like text (Radford et al., 2019; Houde et al., 2020).

Generative AI has immense potential in various domains, including logistics, transportation, travel, healthcare, marketing, and client segmentation (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Generative AI can learn to mimic any distribution of data, creating worlds similar to our own. In logistics, Generative AI can accurately convert satellite images to map views, enabling the exploration of unexplored locations. In travel, Generative AI can create full-face pictures of passengers, improve face identification and verification systems, and enhance upselling and cross-selling strategies. However, generative AI requires modelling to create artefacts from real-world content.

In the sphere of conversational marketing, Generative AI has largely manifested in the form of advanced chatbots or virtual assistants. Unlike rule-based chatbots that rely on pre-programmed responses, Generative AI chatbots are capable of understanding, learning from, and responding to human input dynamically. They leverage natural language processing and machine learning techniques to understand customer queries, learn from past interactions, and generate human-like responses in real-time (Nuruzzaman & Hussain, 2018).

The deployment of Generative AI in conversational marketing has multiple benefits. Firstly, it allows for around-the-clock customer service. AI-powered chatbots can handle customer inquiries instantaneously and continuously, thus offering a higher level of customer service that is not constrained by time zones or human capacity (Umamaheswari & Valarmathi, 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023). Secondly, Generative AI facilitates personalization at scale. It can learn from each interaction, remember customer preferences, and tailor responses to individual customer needs, enhancing the customer experience.

The Future of Conversational Marketing with Generative AI. As Generative AI continues to evolve, its role in shaping conversational marketing strategies is becoming increasingly profound. More sophisticated models are being developed that can handle more complex conversations, understand the context better, and generate more relevant and engaging responses.

Moreover, Generative AI is beginning to integrate with other technologies, such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR), to create more immersive and interactive conversational experiences. With these advancements, the potential of Generative AI in conversational marketing is immense, promising to deliver more personalized, engaging, and effective customer experiences (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

However, it's also important to address the challenges and ethical considerations related to Generative AI, including data privacy, AI transparency, and the potential for AI-generated misinformation or deception. As the field continues to advance, it will be crucial to navigate these issues to fully harness the potential of Generative AI in conversational marketing.

Anthropomorphism and its Psychological Drivers

Anthropomorphism is a term that comes from the Greek terms *anthrōpos* (ἄνθρωπος), which means "human," and *morphē*, which means "shape" or "form." This term refers to more than

only the practice of attributing life to nonliving things, which is known as animism. To be involved in anthropomorphism, one must move beyond the practice of describing actions, whether imagined or observed.

Scholars from a wide variety of fields have pointed out for a very long time that humans have a tendency to view nonhuman agents as being humanlike (Horowitz & Bekoff, 2007; Epley, Waytz & Cacioppo, 2007; Murphy, Gretzel & Pesonen, 2019; Wan & Chen, 2021; Crolig et al., 2022). Anthropomorphic explanations have been called into question as to whether or not they have an appropriate place in scientific discourse, and whether or not anthropomorphism can account for phenomena ranging from religious belief to successful marketing campaigns.

Anthropomorphism is the attribution of human-like characteristics, intentions, emotions, or behaviours to non-human entities or objects (Epley, Waytz, & Cacioppo, 2007). The concept is foundational in human cognition and is often automatic and unconscious (Guthrie, 1993). In the realm of artificial intelligence, and particularly in conversational marketing, anthropomorphism is utilized to design and implement conversational agents that mimic human-like qualities, fostering a sense of familiarity and improving the overall user experience.

The psychological drivers underpinning anthropomorphism have been researched extensively, resulting in several theories that shed light on its mechanisms. Epley et al. (2007) proposed a three-factor theory, which suggests that anthropomorphism is driven by the human need to understand and control the environment, the innate human sociality, and effectance, or the motivation to interact effectively with one's environment.

The *first* driver, the need to understand and control one's environment, manifests in an inclination to humanize the unknown or unfamiliar (Waytz, Cacioppo, & Epley, 2010). When faced with an unknown or unfamiliar object, humans tend to attribute human characteristics to it in an effort to make sense of it and exert control over it (Guthrie, 1993). In the context of conversational marketing, this driver plays a pivotal role. As conversational agents become more complex and capable, users may not fully understand their workings and thus anthropomorphize them to feel a sense of familiarity and control.

The *second* driver, innate human sociality, refers to humans' inherent need to engage socially. Humans are social creatures and tend to perceive the environment in social terms (Epley et al., 2007). This sociality leads us to attribute human-like qualities to non-human entities, facilitating the formation of social connections. In conversational marketing, this driver can be leveraged to foster a sense of connection between users and conversational agents, which could improve user engagement and satisfaction.

The *third* driver, effectance motivation, is the desire to interact effectively with the environment (White, 1959; Pfeuffer et al., 2019; Nicolas & Agnieszka, 2021). This driver can lead to anthropomorphism when human-like characteristics are attributed to non-human entities, facilitating effective interaction (Epley et al., 2007). In the context of conversational

marketing, this can mean designing conversational agents that are not only human-like but are also perceived as competent and capable, thus satisfying users' need for effective interaction.

By understanding and incorporating these psychological drivers of anthropomorphism in the design of conversational agents, businesses can boost customer engagement and build meaningful relationships. Through the creation of human-like, contextually accurate conversational agents, the user's sense of familiarity, social connection, and efficacy are nurtured, leading to improved user experience and potentially increased customer loyalty.

Implications of Anthropomorphic Generative AI on Conversational Marketing

Anthropomorphic Generative AI has presented transformative opportunities within the sphere of conversational marketing. Conversational agents with human-like characteristics are not merely tools for communication but have evolved to play a more sophisticated role in shaping the dynamics of customer-business interaction.

The primary strength of anthropomorphic Generative AI lies in its ability to build and maintain a human-like interaction in a conversational marketing context. This, in turn, has profound implications for marketers as they strive to strengthen relationships with customers and gain a competitive advantage in the marketplace (Van Doorn et al., 2017).

The impact of anthropomorphic design within AI systems has transformed the interactive landscape, creating more effective dialogues that closely mimic human conversations. The ability of these AI-powered agents to understand and respond in a contextually accurate manner enhances the perceived authenticity of interaction, which is a significant factor in conversational marketing.

Furthermore, Generative AI's capacity for learning and evolving over time allows it to create more personalized, relevant, and valuable dialogues. By collecting and analyzing data from interactions, these AI systems can refine their responses to closely match human conversation patterns. This capability also leads to more dynamic and robust conversations that extend beyond pre-scripted dialogues, enabling marketers to create meaningful and impactful dialogues with customers.

However, the integration of anthropomorphic design and Generative AI in conversational marketing does not come without challenges. The prospect of AI systems closely mimicking human conversation raises concerns around user dissonance and perceived deception. The anthropomorphic design may create high expectations in users for human-like interaction, and any shortcomings in meeting these expectations could lead to dissatisfaction and a sense of deception (Ciechanowski et al., 2019).

Balance in Anthropomorphic Conversational Marketing. Balancing the application of anthropomorphism within conversational marketing is a delicate task. It requires a thoughtful approach that goes beyond simply incorporating human-like characteristics into AI systems.

The design and capabilities of conversational agents must be in sync with user expectations. This balance is vital in avoiding dissonance or perceptions of deception that may arise from over-embellishing the AI's capabilities. An appropriately anthropomorphized AI can lead to better interaction quality, user satisfaction, and ultimately, a more effective marketing strategy (Jakesch et al., 2019).

It is necessary, then, to strike a balance between incorporating the human-like traits that users find appealing and managing expectations regarding the AI's capabilities. Too much anthropomorphism can lead to unrealistic expectations, while too little can make the AI feel impersonal and mechanical.

Harmonizing Design and Capabilities of Conversational Agents with User Expectations

A critical takeaway from the study is the need to harmonize the design and capabilities of anthropomorphic Generative AI within the realm of conversational marketing, to align with user expectations. This harmonization is pivotal in mitigating user dissonance or perceived deception and fostering a positive user experience.

A critical aspect of harmonizing the design and capabilities of conversational agents with user expectations is understanding and addressing the "uncanny valley" phenomenon. Coined by robotics professor Masahiro Mori in 1970, the term "uncanny valley" refers to the discomfort people feel when robotic and digital entities closely resemble humans but are not entirely convincing (Mori, MacDorman, & Kageki, 2012). This issue is directly relevant to anthropomorphic Generative AI in conversational marketing.

Anthropomorphic AI systems designed to mimic human conversation are more effective in engaging users, as they leverage familiar forms of interaction. However, if an AI system is overly anthropomorphized and fails to fully live up to the expectations of a human-like interaction, it may cause user dissonance and discomfort, leading users into the uncanny valley. In other words, the more human-like the AI appears, the higher the user's expectations for a human-like interaction. Any discrepancies can lead to a perceived deception (Jakesch et al., 2019). To circumnavigate the uncanny valley, designers and developers must balance the degree of anthropomorphism employed in AI systems. The design should aim for a relatable and intuitive interaction without overstepping into the realm of seeming too human-like, thus managing user expectations. Further, the capabilities of these systems, particularly their limitations, should be transparently communicated to users, to avoid setting unrealistic expectations and mitigate the risk of dissonance or perceived deception (Ciechanowski et al., 2019).

The proposal argues for a careful calibration of anthropomorphism, which would involve designing AI systems that closely mimic human conversation, while also ensuring these systems are transparent about their non-human nature. This is essential to prevent a sense of perceived deception among users, who might otherwise expect these systems to understand and respond like a human in all aspects of interaction (Jakesch et al., 2019).

The integration of anthropomorphic design in AI systems should not aim to deceive users into thinking they are interacting with a human. Instead, the goal should be to make interactions more intuitive and enjoyable, thus improving user engagement and satisfaction. For this reason, the design of anthropomorphic AI systems should focus on aspects of human interaction that users find useful, while the capabilities of these systems should be clearly communicated to users.

Conversational agents need to be smart, but not too smart, as overestimated intelligence could potentially lead to user dissonance. If users expect the AI to understand and respond to complex or ambiguous requests based on its perceived intelligence, and the AI fails to do so, it could lead to frustration and dissonance. Therefore, managing user expectations regarding the capabilities of these AI systems is crucial (Ciechanowski et al., 2019).

It is vital to strike a balance between the anthropomorphic design and the capabilities of conversational agents in the context of user expectations. This balance is key to creating an engaging, satisfying user experience that drives the efficacy of conversational marketing while minimizing the potential for user dissonance or perceived deception.

Exploring Future Research Directions in Anthropomorphic Generative AI for Conversational Marketing

The evolution of Anthropomorphic Generative AI in the field of conversational marketing offers a plethora of research directions. This paper presents an in-depth exploration of potential research proposals in five major areas: User Expectations and Acceptance of Anthropomorphic AI, Anthropomorphic AI Design and Implementation, Ethical and Legal Implications, Impact on Business Outcomes, and Technological Advancements. Each domain offers a unique lens through which we can further understand the design, application, implications, and potential of anthropomorphic AI within the context of conversational marketing.

Let's dive a bit deeper into each of these directions and expand them further:

User Expectations and Acceptance of Anthropomorphic AI

- In-depth analysis of the cognitive and emotional factors that shape user expectations and acceptance of anthropomorphic AI.
- Understanding the socio-cultural, demographic, and psychological variables that influence how different users perceive and interact with anthropomorphic AI.
- Investigation of user experience design principles that promote user acceptance and engagement with anthropomorphic AI.

2. Anthropomorphic AI Design and Implementation

- Experimental research to determine the optimal balance of anthropomorphism in AI to ensure engagement without crossing into the "uncanny valley".
- Case studies of successful and unsuccessful implementations of anthropomorphic AI in conversational marketing to identify best practices and common pitfalls.
- Exploration of the role of interdisciplinary teams (including psychologists, sociologists, marketers, and AI specialists) in the design and implementation of anthropomorphic AI.

3. Ethical and Legal Implications

- Longitudinal studies to understand the long-term ethical implications of anthropomorphic AI, including potential risks for privacy, autonomy, and consent.
- Comparative analysis of legal regulations across different regions and industries to identify potential gaps and opportunities for policy development.

4. Impact on Business Outcomes

- Quantitative studies to measure the impact of anthropomorphic AI on key business metrics such as customer engagement, retention, and conversion rates.
- Cost-benefit analysis and ROI studies of businesses that have implemented anthropomorphic AI in their marketing strategies.

5. Technological Advancements

- Research into the potential application of cutting-edge technologies (like quantum computing, advanced NLP, and sentiment analysis) to enhance the capabilities of anthropomorphic AI.
- Predictive modelling to anticipate future technological trends and their impact on the design and implementation of anthropomorphic AI in conversational marketing.

Table 1. Enhanced future research directions of anthropomorphic generative AI for Conversational Marketing

<i>Research Area</i>	<i>Specific Research Directions</i>
<i>User Expectations and Acceptance of Anthropomorphic AI</i>	In-depth analysis of cognitive and emotional factors; Socio-cultural, demographic, and psychological influences; User experience design principles
<i>Anthropomorphic AI</i>	Experimental research on anthropomorphism balance; Case

<i>Design and Implementation</i>	studies for best practices; Role of interdisciplinary teams
<i>Ethical and Legal Implications</i>	Longitudinal studies on ethical implications; Comparative analysis of legal regulations
<i>Impact on Business Outcomes</i>	Quantitative studies on business metrics; Cost-benefit analysis and ROI studies
<i>Technological Advancements</i>	Research into the potential application of cutting-edge technologies; Predictive modelling for future trends

This expanded roadmap provides a more detailed guide for future research, catering to a wider range of potential investigative studies and methodologies. It thereby enables a broader and more profound understanding of anthropomorphic Generative AI in the context of conversational marketing.

CONCLUSION

The implications of Anthropomorphic Generative AI in the domain of conversational marketing open new vistas of opportunity, propelling a shift in the dynamics of customer-business interaction. However, these sophisticated dialogues, simulating human-like conversations, have sparked a set of unique challenges and ethical considerations.

Our exploration underlines the need for harmonization of design, capabilities, and user expectations to create effective, satisfying interactions while minimizing the potential for user dissonance or perceived deception. This delicate balance requires a thoughtful approach to anthropomorphization, ensuring the AI maintains a relatable and intuitive interaction without creating an illusion of being overly human-like.

The potential future research directions discussed extend the understanding of how AI can be designed to maximize the effectiveness of conversational marketing. These proposals cover areas such as understanding user preferences in AI-human interactions, the ethical considerations of using anthropomorphic design, addressing the uncanny valley phenomenon, and the impact of cultural and societal factors.

As AI technologies continue to evolve, it is crucial for researchers and practitioners to remain agile, constantly evaluating the balance between AI's anthropomorphism and user expectations. Future research in these areas will be instrumental in shaping the successful integration of Anthropomorphic Generative AI into the conversational marketing landscape, optimizing user engagement, and creating a more personalized, immersive conversational experience.

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